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KNOWLEDGE AND USE OF THE INTERNET FOR ADOLESCENT
HEALTH EDUCATION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

This exploratory study investigated nurse practitioners' (NPs') use of the Internet with regard to online health information available to adolescents. It assessed their knowledge of websites, whether they asked their adolescent patients about Internet resources, and if they knew how to ascertain appropriate websites. Participants in this project were practicing NPs who currently saw adolescents in their practice setting. Data were collected through survey methodology and analysis was done on 23 respondents. Study findings showed that most of the NPs surveyed had access to a computer and the Internet, were confident with technology, and were fairly knowledgeable about locating and judging Internet health information. They believed using technology would make their job easier and enhance the teaching time spent with adolescents. NPs did not routinely ask adolescents about websites, and the NPs who did refer teens to specific websites were more knowledgeable about workplace policies, searching out websites, and knowing specific websites. The top three responses regarding barriers to use in practice included time constraints, lack of adolescent access to a computer at worksite or home, and the adolescent's unclear knowledge of information found online. The top two facilitators reported were the availability of having a computer, smartphone, and/or the provider's willingness to improve the care to adolescents. The top three benefits of using health websites with adolescents were an increase in knowledge by using appropriate websites, a health awareness that may change behaviors, and the educating of peers and

family members who also look at websites. The most frequently listed disadvantages included language/literacy differences and possible self-diagnosis. The perceptions of usefulness and ease of use of websites by NPs will lead to the integration of health websites into their current practice. The comfort and knowledge of appropriate websites to refer adolescents to are essential in the NP's successful use in practice. It is important to recognize the need for health education websites as a routine part of an adolescent's visit to the NP. It is also practical to devise a tool to assist a nurse practitioner in locating, evaluating, and referring adolescents to appropriate websites.

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BACKGROUND

Health education and health promotion activities are essential elements in maintaining the health of our population. Education is an important component of quality care that is provided to clients in order to promote healthy lifestyle changes, enhance compliance with medical recommendations, and ensure that accurate health information is given.

Working with different populations of varying age, gender, race, and ethnicity can bring with it different approaches and formats for educating. Some clients learn from hearing the information, some from watching videos, some from actively participating, and others from reading—either in paper form or online. Many clients learn from a combination of teaching techniques. With the growing use of the Internet and social media by the lay public as a means to obtain information, these tools can provide an opportunity to incorporate technologic modalities into a practice setting. Today, a large portion of the population uses the Internet and social networking sites as resources for information. According to the U.S. Census Bureau in 2010, 76% of households in the United States have a computer. In the Pew Internet Summer Tracking Survey (2012), 81% of adults use the Internet. A large portion of adult users (80%) use it for looking up health or medical information. When investigating practices in the adolescent population, 95% of teens use the Internet. According to the Pew Internet and American Life Project (Lenhart, Purcell, Smith, & Zickuhr, 2010), “Approximately 31% of adolescents ages 12-17 use the internet to look for health, dieting and physical fitness information” (para. 2).

The Internet is replete with health information websites that cover a variety of topics but picking the right site can be a daunting task, especially for teens. For adolescents, health education online may even replace the use of written material/pamphlets because the convenience of searching out information quickly and knowing that the information is accurate can create a safe learning environment for teens. The privacy issue is another benefit of online information.

Adolescents receiving care in a health setting come not only for medical attention but also for health information. However, adolescent may not want their parents to know they are seeking information or care and possibly may not want to leave the health care setting with pamphlets that describe their needs, including sexually transmitted infection or birth control information as examples. The use of online resources allows new channels of communication and education capable of making a positive change in health behaviors.

With teens accessing information online, there is an obligation by providers and parents to be knowledgeable about credible online resources to recommend to adolescents. These trustworthy sites need to provide the adolescent with up-to-date and accurate information in an informative and interactive way. Advanced practice nurses as primary care providers who work with the teen population need to be familiar with and comfortable discussing appropriate websites for health information. In today's health care setting, the question remains as to whether providers are seizing the opportunity to discuss these Internet resources during health care visits with their patients.

The purpose of this project was to investigate what primary care nurse practitioners know about health education information that adolescents ages 13-18 seek

from the Internet. It represented an inquiry into whether nurse practitioners know what health education websites teens are using and also if nurse practitioners are recommending any particular sites to adolescents. Another aspect of this investigation was to assess how comfortable nurse practitioners are with exploring the Internet to find health websites that provide reliable and trustworthy health education to share with adolescents.

Problem Statement

There is paucity of information about health care providers', specifically nurse practitioners', use of Internet resources to provide health education to adolescent patients. Thus, this project was designed to explore nurse practitioners' use of the Internet with regard to their computer use and skill set, their knowledge of appropriate and practical online health information available to adolescents, and whether they routinely asked their adolescent patient about what Internet resources or websites the teen uses to obtain health information. Other factors explored included the comfort level of nurse practitioners related to Internet health website content and the confidence nurse practitioners had in recommending appropriate websites to adolescents.

Research Questions

This study attempted to answer the following research questions:

1. What facilitators and barriers did nurse practitioners identify about their computer use and skill level related to using information technology in their practice setting?
2. What did nurse practitioners perceive as the advantages and disadvantages of adolescent use of online health education websites?

3. What was nurse practitioners' level of knowledge of health education websites that adolescents were seeking out, what health websites were available and appropriate for use in the practice setting, and how did they ascertain which websites were appropriate to recommend to adolescents?

Purpose Statement

Adolescents are seeking health information from the Internet, especially sexual health information, and rely on social media, websites, and mobile applications for health information. Consequently, providers must be able to assist them in choosing credible sites and making sense of the information that they find. With limited studies available that address whether nurse practitioners are using Internet resources with adolescents or asking their adolescent patients what sites teens explore in regard to health care information, the need for this study is apparent. Thus, the purpose of this doctoral project was to explore nurse practitioners' use of the Internet to provide teens with health care information and nurse practitioners' knowledge of Internet websites used by adolescents for health information. A secondary gain from this study were the data collected that can be used to learn how to best assist nurse practitioners in recommending reliable websites and information technology resources to adolescents.

The nurse practitioner can learn how to incorporate health websites as an educational tool for adolescents and communicate health education via a form of technology that adolescents are familiar with and commonly employ to secure information. There are opportunities to use the adolescent's interest and skill in using the Internet as a health education tool that will direct the teen to trustworthy and age appropriate information sites. The larger potential benefit in using trustworthy resources

available on the Internet is that of empowering adolescents with knowledge that can lead to behavior changes and facilitate health promotion.

Supporting Framework

The foundation for this study evolved from two models, both of which served as a framework to guide this study. The social ecological model is a conceptual framework that addresses the health education/promotion aspect of adolescent care; the technology acceptance model attends to the acceptance of the role of Internet technology by the health care provider in offering health care education to teens. The social ecological model is based on the public health perspective of health promotion. Within this model, health is determined by influences at multiple levels. An individual's behavior is the "outcome of interest and behavior viewed as being determined by the following five environments" (McLeroy, Bibeau, Steckler, & Glanz, 1988, p. 355). These environments include the intrapersonal factors, interpersonal processes, institutional factors, community factors, and public policy.

The individual's behavior is the first area discussed. This includes the attitudes and skills and knowledge that an individual possesses. In addition, the adolescent's ability to access information online, the comfort with technology, and also the health literacy level of the adolescent should be considered.

The next level involves the interpersonal processes, namely relationships with family, friends, and health care providers that influence the individual. Providers making recommendations on healthy behaviors or recommendations of health education websites are some examples. Contacts on the Internet through Facebook or other online social networking sites as well as peer pressure at school can influence health behaviors. These

are examples of face-to-face and online relationships with friends that are key motivators (peer pressure) in the lives of teens.

Institutional or organizational factors are the next area of influence. Health care clinics and health promotion programs at school and/or work are examples. Computer management systems that include patient portals, health education sites, education referral tools, and reminders from the provider can help support the individual. Communities can sponsor educational programs and community groups that can promote supportive relationships. A community can also be an online social networking site, support group, or blog. The local library with computer and/or Internet access, local Boys and Girls Clubs of America, and a large organization like Kaiser with the information network are other examples of community factors.

The last area of influence encompasses public policy. This may involve laws to protect the health of a whole community. Policies that surround the ethics of Internet use, privacy, and the guidelines for appropriate Internet patient-provider relationship are some of the many issues to be addressed.

The second model laying the foundation for this project addresses the health care providers' use of technology in providing health care. The technology acceptance model, established by Davis in 1989, has been widely used to describe informational technology usefulness (Holden & Karsh, 2010; Ketikidis, Dimitrovski, Lazuras, & Bath, 2012; Kurki, Koivunen, Anttila, Hatonen, & Valimaki, 2011). In Davis's original work, which focused on the realm of business information technology, he recognized that workers were not always using information technology that was available to them. He identified the variables of attitude, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use as the primary

influences in people's decisions to use information technology (Davis, 1989; Holden & Karsh, 2010; Ketikidis et al., 2012; Kurki et al., 2011). In this study, the technology acceptance model has been adapted for use with nurse practitioners. Figure 1 illustrates key principles in this adapted model. With the use of computer systems in both hospital and office settings, it is important to recognize the need to evaluate the health care professional's acceptance of information technology and its benefit as another resource that has merit for patient education.

Figure 1. Nurse practitioner technology acceptance model. Adapted from technology acceptance model (Davis, 1989).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

The Internet is an easy and convenient way to search out information and gain access to many different topics of interest for both adults and adolescents. Many private, nonprofit, and government organizations have created health websites and tailored their websites to adolescents to disseminate information on a variety of subjects. There have been a number of recent studies that have evaluated where adolescents go for their health information and also in what manner they want to receive their health information. These studies are presented in this review of the literature. Other facets of research related to Internet use by health care providers featured in this review are their comfort with using the Internet and how this technology can be used to educate the adolescent population. Thus, this review of the literature discusses what research has revealed about teens using the Internet for health care information and health care providers' use of technology as an adjunct in their efforts to educate patients.

Adolescents and Online Resources

Adolescence is a prime time for health care education and is marked by a cadre of health education needs, including anticipatory guidance related to body development, exposure to drugs and alcohol, sexual health, sexually transmitted infections, nutrition and exercise, mental health issues, and stress. To answer their questions about these topics, many teens turn to the Internet for information. Research has demonstrated adolescents are utilizing the Internet more and more as a resource to obtain facts about health. The Pew Internet Summer Tracking Survey (2012) showed approximately one out of six adolescents seek health information about sensitive topics like sexual health,

drug use, and mental health issues by accessing the Internet. The use of mobile phones to access information is another common way for adolescents to acquire knowledge from the Internet, especially among minority groups. According to Lenhart et al. (2010), 40% of Hispanics and 48% of African Americans use their mobile phones to access the Internet compared with 31% of Whites. Whether it is from the mobile phone or computer, teens are online seeking knowledge about an array of topics.

In a qualitative study by Smart, Parker, Lampert, and Sulo (2012), 11 groups of adolescents ages 13-17 years participated in a focused interview session to evaluate their “health education needs and how they prefer to receive health information” (p. 380). A convenience sample of 101 boys and girls from varied cultural backgrounds were divided into groups of seven to 11 students. The group sessions lasted approximately 40 minutes. Students were asked about their learning needs and preferences for obtaining health information. Participants most often discussed topics about certain diseases, health behaviors, and mental health concerns and noted they would use either communication with trusted individuals or the Internet to gain information. These adolescents also revealed that they want health information that is easy to access, accurate, immediate, private, easy to understand, and anonymous.

In a study by Selkie, Benson, and Moreno (2011), adolescent views were queried in regard to new technology and sexual health education. The investigators used a mixed-methods grounded study approach with group interviews and surveys. Twenty-nine adolescents participated in both the survey and interview. The ages of the participants ranged from 14 to 19 years, with 65% of them being female. Over half of the adolescents were sexually active and almost all of them utilized the Internet and had a

profile on a social networking site. The three themes that emerged from the focus groups were adolescents' desire for sexual health education that is (a) easily accessible, (b) both credible and confidential, and (c) offered in a way that is nonthreatening (Selkie et al., 2011).

Internet resources have been demonstrated to be a beneficial tool that can be used to educate adolescents. Internet technology provides information in a way that teens respond to and serves as a medium that promotes opportunity for health behavior and attitude changes. A key study that has demonstrated these positive health benefits was conducted by Ybarra and Suman (2008). According to Ybarra and Suman's research on reasons and actions taken after obtaining Internet health information, they found almost half of the adolescents had contacted a health care provider as a result. The data source for this research was from *Surveying the Digital Future, Year 4*; their sample size was 2,007 respondents. Of this sample, 37 subjects were 12-19 years of age. A Kaiser Family Foundation survey titled *Generation X.com: How Young People Use the Internet for Health Information* reported one out of seven young people ($n = 820$) who sought out information online contacted a health care provider because of what the adolescent found (Rideout, 2001). Furthermore, data from this survey showed that 39% of young people who sought out information on the Internet changed their behavior because of information they discovered online (Rideout, 2001).

Health Care Providers and Online Resources

Providing education is an essential component of an advanced practice nurse's skill set, and health promotion and illness prevention are an integral part of patient education. The utilization of the Internet as an educational tool can be adapted to all age

groups of patients in different formats. With adolescent Internet utilization being so commonplace, the question remains as to what providers are doing to incorporate information technology resources into their plan of care. Studies have shown that health care providers do not often recommend specific health care websites to patients. There are many reasons for this resistance. McMullan (2006) reviewed a number of articles and discovered that health care providers are concerned about the content of the information on the Internet. The providers worried about their patients' ability to understand the information, the accuracy of the information retrieved from the Internet, and their patients' capacity to misdiagnose themselves. Time constraints in a consultation and medical authority being challenged were noted by some physicians as their reasons for not referring patients to Internet resources for health information.

In a review of the literature, Wald, Dube, and Anthony (2007) noted that there are a number of possible disadvantages to using the Internet for health information as reported in the studies they reviewed. They listed a number of problematic areas, including the following: the quality of information online can be variable, certain patient groups may have limited access, websites may impact liability for providers, and the Internet may interfere with the physician-patient relationship.

Another broader aspect to be considered is the comfort level of health care providers when using computers and the Internet as well as their attitudes toward information technology in general. Kurki et al. (2011) designed an exploratory qualitative study to investigate psychiatric nurses' perceptions of the usefulness of the Internet in an outpatient care setting with adolescents suffering from depression. Through focus group discussions with 12 nurses, the researchers identified some distinct

categories related to the benefits and disadvantages of Internet use in the care of the adolescent with depression as well as facilitators and barriers influencing the nurse's use of the Internet. Specific benefits of Internet usage with adolescents were supporting the self-management of the adolescent, creating a supportive nurse-adolescent interaction, and creating an environment that encouraged adolescent involvement and gave appropriate and confidential content for the adolescent's needs. Disadvantages identified when the Internet was added as a patient care tool included changes in the relationship—as discussions were no longer face to face and nonbeneficial changes to the format of the nurse-patient intervention—and the type of depression was too severe for this modality to be used effectively. Other negative effects related to teens using the Internet were increased dependency on the computer, potential for increased contact with strangers (e.g., unsavory chat rooms that offer *group support*), and the inability to confirm trustworthiness of Internet sites.

Facilitators to the use of the Internet by nurses identified by Kurki et al. (2011) consisted of the nurse's belief that it provided a source of knowledge, a positive attitude toward the Internet, and adequate resources related to the use of information technology (e.g., training, room, laptop, solving security challenges). Barriers noted in this study were lack of training, time, or instructions; technical problems; a negative attitude toward the Internet; uncertainty of protection under the law; and the ethical issue of suicide risk of the depressed adolescent.

Some health care providers struggle with the quality of the information on the Internet and have doubts about how it will benefit the patient. In a study by Emond, Groot, Wetzels, and van Osch (2013), the researchers investigated Dutch health care

providers' opinions and behaviors when referring cancer patients to Internet information. The sample consisted of 76 oncologists and 54 oncology nurses. The researchers employed an exploratory approach utilizing a questionnaire developed from relevant literature. The results revealed that three of the most frequently stated reasons for not referring a patient to a particular website were that providers were unsure about the quality of the information, they were unfamiliar with websites that are available, and they had ambiguity about the value of the websites for the patient.

Conclusion

Health care providers have not yet realized the full potential that the Internet has to offer when it comes to health education. Apprehension in using Internet resources stems from many sources including lack of knowledge as to what is available online, uncertainty with content and credibility of websites, and also questions regarding the usefulness of the Internet. Adolescents recognize that the Internet is a valuable tool in gaining knowledge in a safe way. However, few studies regarding nurse practitioners and their knowledge of health education websites to recommend to adolescents have been conducted. Nurse practitioners are an influential source of health education for the adolescent. Through appropriate guidance, teens can safely navigate health information online. Providers also need guidance as to how to evaluate websites and choose the most appropriate and accurate ones and they may also need help in finding value in the use of the Internet.

METHODS

Design

An exploratory study design was used in this study to investigate barriers and facilitators identified by nurse practitioners related to their use of Internet resources and websites in providing health education materials to teens (defined for this project as a patient 13-18 years of age). In addition, this researcher investigated whether nurse practitioners ask their adolescent clients about what Internet sites and what resources teens are using. Data were collected through a survey methodology and provided insight about the need for nurse practitioners to be aware of the sites their teen clients seek health information from and how they can more effectively interact with teens in using valuable online health information in their practice.

Protection of Human Rights

This proposal, the survey tool, and a corresponding consent form were approved by the California State University of Long Beach Institutional Review Board (IRB). Recruitment of subjects was conducted through the local chapter of the California Association of Nurse Practitioners (CANP); written consent was given by the Orange County Chapter President for this researcher to seek out local CANP members to participate in this study. Additional subjects were recruited through networking by word of mouth.

Sample

Participants in this project were practicing nurse practitioners in specialty areas of women's health, pediatrics, or family practice who saw adolescents in their practice setting. After IRB approval, a convenient sample of nurse practitioners was asked to

complete a questionnaire. The participants were recruited through CANP by announcement(s) on their organization Facebook page, by e-mail notification, and by this researcher reaching out to and contacting CANP members at local meetings. Additional recruitment of participants was conducted through network sampling.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire was developed based on a literature review of surveys involving computer literacy, technology, Internet use, and online health information. The key points selected for survey question items were derived from studies discussed in the review of literature. The questionnaire had 37 questions and took approximately 15 minutes to complete. The information obtained included basic demographic data, years in practice, computer use, exposure to health education websites, knowledge of adolescent Internet use, and questions addressing barriers and possible facilitators to the use of the Internet for health education with the adolescent. The tool developed by this researcher, Health Education Information on the Internet (HEII; Appendix A), contained questions using a 5-point Likert scale and yes-no responses. A section at the end of the survey included four open-ended questions. Each participant gave written consent before filling out the questionnaire. The consent explained the purpose, risks and benefits, voluntary participation, and confidentiality of the questionnaire (Appendix B).

Questions related to the content and focus area of the HEII were derived from the following studies: the work of Davis (1989) related to usefulness and ease of use of technology and the research by Kurki et al. (2011) identifying facilitators and barriers as well as advantages and disadvantages for both usage of Internet with patients and the

nurses' use of the Internet. These two studies provided the ideas about content and the focus of the tool developed for this study.

Prior to data collection, the first iteration of the questionnaire was given to two expert nurse practitioners whose practice involves health care delivery to adolescents. Each had over 20 years of experience in health delivery to teens. One information technology expert with a 5-year history of working with adolescents in an educational institution was also consulted regarding technology-based issues. The survey tool was tested for validity by sending the survey to two nurse practitioner experts who worked with adolescents to review for adolescent-based issues. They were asked to evaluate the content as to whether each question addressed the facilitators, barriers, advantages, or disadvantages by responding *yes* or *no*. They were also asked to identify any other critical factors they believed were not included in this survey and any unclear or unnecessary questions. For each question in the survey, the experts were asked to answer whether it addressed a critical factor (yes or no), clarity (yes or no), and necessity (needed or not needed). A comment section was provided for additional items the experts believed should be included. The experts were in 91% agreement on the clarity of the items within the questionnaire. They were in 98% agreement on necessity of questions and 80% on the coverage of critical factors within the questionnaire. One expert suggested further definition of four of the terms used in the questionnaire, which resulted in a rewording of four questions. Suggestions from the information technology expert yielded two additional items that were added to the questionnaire related to technology equipment. This represented the researcher's validity testing of the tool.

An additional two nurse practitioners were asked to participate as part of reliability testing. They completed the survey twice; the second completion was done 4 days after the initial completion to evaluate reliability of the questions through test-retest reliability. The first nurse practitioner's test had 83% similarity from test one to test two. The second nurse practitioner had a similarity score of 88% from test one to test two.

Procedures (Protocol)

The questionnaire, HEII, was launched on SurveyMonkey™ as well as in paper form. Consent was obtained from each participant prior to completing the survey. Participants viewed an announcement of the project and a request to participate via the CANP Facebook page. An announcement of the project was also done at a local meeting of CANP. Permission was granted from CANP to place an announcement on the organization's website Facebook page and to also announce the survey at local meetings. Participants were asked to complete the survey online via a link to SurveyMonkey™ or a survey could be requested via email or in person. A paper form of the survey was also available at a CANP meeting for any member who requested a written survey; participants completing the HEII survey were instructed to place their completed survey in a collection envelope available at the meeting site. Participants recruited at the meeting site were also given the option of obtaining a self-addressed stamped envelope depending on preference. Data collection was for 2 months from December 2013 through February 2014.

Analysis

At the end of the data collection period, the data were placed into a database and coded. The questions were placed into categories based on the concepts being

investigated. The categories identified were demographics, accessibility to technology, use, confidence, usefulness related to technology, adolescent communication issues, and nurse practitioner knowledge as related to health education on the Internet. The identified barriers and facilitators for the use of health education websites as educational resources in the workplace as well as the benefits and disadvantages to using health education websites with adolescents were also analyzed. Descriptive statistics, *t* tests, and Spearman's correlation and post-hoc analysis were used to analyze the data.

RESULTS

The questionnaire was completed by 23 nurse practitioners. Of these nurse practitioners, 18 took the survey online via SurveyMonkey™. The other five took a paper and pencil version, one being returned via U.S. mail.

Sample

The characteristics of the sample are presented in Table 1. The ages of the subjects ranged from 31 to 65 years, with the majority (39.1%) of respondents being in the 46- to 50-year range. They were 91.3% female and 8.7% male. Over half of the respondents (56.5%) identified themselves as White. The others indicated they were Latino/Hispanic (13.0%), Black or African American (13.0%), Pacific Islander (4.3%), Vietnamese/Vietnamese American (4.3%), and other (8.7%). Subjects in this study worked mainly in the specialty areas of family practice (47.8%), obstetrics/gynecology (21.7%), and pediatrics (8.7%). Five of the respondents were from other specialty areas. The practice settings for these practitioners varied and included ambulatory/primary care (34.8%), private practice (34.8%), community/school clinic (17.4%), retail health (4.3%), and hospital (4.3%). Within these practices, the nurse practitioners in this sample saw a mean of 23 adolescents ($SD = 26.8$) each week for health care visits.

Computer/Internet Access

As demonstrated in Table 2, all of the nurse practitioners in this sample had computer and Internet access at home (100.0%) and at work (100.0%), and a majority of them (78.3%) used electronic medical record in their practice settings. A small percentage (13.0%) did not have Internet access available at all times in the workplace.

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Sample (N = 23)

Demographic	<i>n</i> (%)
Gender	
Male	2 (8.7%)
Female	21 (91.3%)
Age	
31-35	1 (4.3%)
36-40	3 (13.0%)
41-45	2 (8.7%)
46-50	9 (39.1%)
51-55	3 (13.0%)
56-60	3 (13.0%)
61-65	2 (8.7%)
Race/Ethnicity	
Black/African American	3 (13.0%)
Latino/Hispanic	3 (13.0%)
Pacific Islander	1 (4.3%)
Vietnamese/Vietnamese American	1 (4.3%)
White	13 (56.5%)
Other	2 (8.7%)
Specialty	
Family practice	11 (47.8%)
Pediatrics	2 (8.7%)
Obstetrics/Gynecology	5 (21.7%)
Other	5 (21.7%)
Practice setting	
Retail health	1 (4.3%)
Ambulatory/Primary care	8 (34.8%)
Community/School clinic	4 (17.4%)
Private practice	8 (34.8%)
Hospital	1 (4.3%)
Other	1 (4.3%)

Note. Reported as frequency (valid %).

Table 2

Nurse Practitioners' Access to Technology

Variable	Setting	
	Home	Work
Access to computer	22 (100.0%)	22 (100.0%)
Access to Internet	23 (100.0%)	23 (100.0%)
Frequency of Internet use		
Daily	23 (100.0%)	18 (81.8%)
Weekly		4 (18.2%)
Monthly		
Use electronic medical records	-	18 (78.3%)
Internet availability		
Not at all	-	0 (0.0%)
Seldom	-	0 (0.0%)
~50% of the time	-	1 (4.3%)
Usually	-	2 (8.7%)
Always	-	20 (87.0%)

Note. Data reported as frequency (valid %).

Of note, over 90% of the respondents in this group stated that they owned a smartphone, desktop computer, and/or a tablet.

Internet Use

Nurse practitioners in this study had to rate the frequency (from 0 *never* to 5 *very frequently*) with which they used the Internet to obtain health information (see Table 3). Over half of the respondents answered that they utilized the Internet *very frequently* (60.9%) to obtain information for either themselves or friends/relatives in the last 1 to 3 months before completing the survey. Only 8.6% of the respondents answered *rarely* or *never* used the Internet for themselves or friends/relatives. Similarly, over half of the respondents used technology *very frequently* (56.5%) to gather information for their

Table 3

Nurse Practitioners' Use of Technology

Used Internet to obtain health information for . . .	Frequency					
	Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently
. . . Self, friends, family (Past month)	1 (4.3%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (4.3%)	4 (17.4%)	3 (13.0%)	14 (60.9%)
. . . Self, friends, family (Past 3 months)	1 (4.3%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (4.3%)	4 (17.4%)	3 (13.0%)	14 (60.9%)
. . . Patients (Past month)	0 (0.0%)	3 (13.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (4.3%)	6 (26.1%)	13 (56.5%)
. . . Patients (Past 3 months)	0 (0.0%)	3 (13.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (8.7%)	6 (26.1%)	12 (52.2%)

Note. Data reported as frequency (valid %). Mode indicated by bold font.

patients in the last month and 52.2% in the last 3 months. Very few nurse practitioners (13.0%) stated that they *very rarely* used the Internet for patients.

Confidence and Usefulness

Confidence levels with computer technology were positive amongst the respondents. Respondents reported their confidence as high, with 87.0% rating themselves as *confident*, *moderately confident*, or *very confident* with using computer technology. There were 43.5% in the *very confident* category and none of them responded *not confident*. A majority of the nurse practitioners reported a very positive degree of confidence when using computer technology to gather trustworthy health education. As seen in Table 4, statements related to confidence were rated on level of agreement (1 being *strongly disagree* to 5 being *strongly agree*). A majority of nurse practitioners (87%) agreed that they could find trustworthy health education on the Internet. They also agreed that they could become skillful at identifying appropriate sites

Table 4

Nurse Practitioners' Confidence Levels With Internet Health Education

For my adolescent patients, I am . . .	Level of Agreement				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Confident using the Internet to gather trustworthy health education (HE)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (13.0%)	8 (34.8%)	12 (52.2%)
Easy for me to become skillful at identifying appropriate websites	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	7 (31.8%)	5 (22.7%)	10 (45.5%)
Concerned about ability to judge the accuracy of Internet health information	6 (26.1%)	11 (47.8%)	3 (13.0%)	3 (13.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Using HE websites would enhance my effectiveness in teaching	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (4.5%)	10 (45.5%)	11 (50.0%)
Using HE websites would make my job easier	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (13.0%)	11 (47.8%)	9 (39.1%)
It would benefit me to identify Internet resources to be accessed by teens	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (4.5%)	10 (45.5%)	11 (50.0%)
Concerned about the ability of adolescents to identify reliable Internet health information	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	8 (34.8%)	15 (65.2%)

Note. Data reported as frequency (valid %). Mode indicated by bold font.

for adolescents (68.2%). A proportion of the respondents (31.8%) were unsure of their ability to develop that skill. None of the subjects believed he or she could not become skilled.

Also investigated were the use and usefulness of health education websites in the workplace. Of note, 87.0% of the nurse practitioners in this study believed health education websites would make their job easier; 95.5% believed it would enhance their effectiveness in teaching adolescents. There was an overall high sense of benefit (95.5%) associated with identifying websites that adolescent patients could access. There was only minor concern from the nurse practitioners (13.0%) about their ability to identify and judge the health education material on the Internet; however, they noted a unanimously strong concern (100.0%) about the adolescent's judgment of what would be considered reliable health information on the Internet. Nurse practitioners in this study responded that they were either slightly likely (26.1%) or quite likely (52.2%) to use the Internet to provide adolescents with health care information handouts or websites.

In order to examine nurse practitioners' perceptions of the usefulness of online health resources, a series of three attitudinal statements scored from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*) were developed, in which higher scores reflected greater usefulness. The decision was made a priori to examine these three items for internal consistency prior to combining them as a scale score. Cronbach's alpha revealed adequate internal consistency ($\alpha = .88$) with single-item deletions making negligible improvements to the scale's internal consistency. As a result, all three questions were combined into a single, overall attitudinal scale with possible scores ranging from 3 to 15 points.

A statistically significant moderate, positive correlation was observed between nurse practitioners' perception of the usefulness of web-based health resources and their use of these resources for both personal and professional use in both the past month and past 3 months (r ranged from .48 to .58, all $ps < .05$).

A statistically significant moderate, positive correlation was observed between nurse practitioners' perceived ease of use of web-based health resources and their frequency of using the information for themselves, friends, or family in both the past month ($r = .55, p = .008$) and past 3 months ($r = .55, p = .008$). Interestingly, while the same pattern was found for nurse practitioners' sharing of web-based health resources for patients in the past 3 months ($r = .51, p = .02$), no significant correlation was observed in the past month ($r = .37, p = .09$).

Adolescent Communication Issues

Nurse practitioners in this study believed that either some or most of the adolescent patients (81.0%) they see in their practice routinely seek out health information on the Internet. Communication of health education on the Internet between the adolescent patient and the nurse practitioner are addressed in Table 5. Adolescents do communicate with their providers about information that they discovered online. A majority of the nurse practitioners in this sample (66.6%) responded that adolescents *occasionally* (38.1%), *frequently* (9.5%), or *very frequently* (19.0%) ask about health information that they obtained from the Internet. A smaller percentage (33.3%) replied that the adolescents *rarely* or *never* ask about information they acquired on the Internet.

Interestingly, adolescents are not routinely asking their providers where to search on the Internet for health information. According to this nurse practitioner sample, a majority of the time (80.9%) adolescents *never* (23.8%), *very rarely* (23.8%), or *rarely* (33.3%) inquire from the nurse practitioner about which Internet resources would be valuable sources for them to access.

Table 5

Adolescent Issues Regarding Health Education on the Internet

	Frequency					
	Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently
Do your adolescent patients ever ask you about health information that they obtained from the Internet?	4 (19.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (14.3%)	8 (38.1%)	2 (9.5%)	4 (19.0%)
Do your adolescent patients ever inquire as to what Internet websites/resources would be valuable health information for them?	5 (23.8%)	5 (23.8%)	7 (33.3%)	2 (9.5%)	2 (9.5%)	0 (0.0%)
Have your adolescent patients talked to you about health education websites?						
Last month	9 (42.9%)	3 (14.3%)	3 (14.3%)	4 (19.0%)	2 (9.5%)	0 (0.0%)
Last 3 months	8 (38.1%)	4 (19.0%)	3 (14.3%)	4 (19.0%)	2 (9.5%)	0 (0.0%)
Have you discussed health websites with your adolescent patients?						
Last month	7 (33.3%)	5 (23.8%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (28.6%)	3 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)
Last 3 months	7 (33.3%)	5 (23.8%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (28.6%)	3 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)

Note. Data reported as frequency (valid %). Mode indicated by bold font.

When these nurse practitioners were asked whether their adolescent patients talked to them about specific health education websites, 71.5% responded with *rarely*, *very rarely*, or *never*. There were 42.9% in the *never* category. Only 28.5% of the nurse practitioners reported that adolescents shared information with them about where they looked online for health information. These same nurse practitioners noted that the top two sites reported being used by their adolescent patients were webmd.com and Google. Nurse practitioners were further queried about whether they discussed health education websites with their adolescent patients; 57.1% responded with *very rarely* or *never*, and 42.9% marked *occasionally* and *frequently*. About half of the respondents (52.4%) indicated they did not recommend specific websites to their adolescent patients. Of those nurse practitioners replying that they did recommend a site (47.6%), the top three most frequently named websites were cdc.gov, webmd.com, and choosemyplate.gov.

Knowledge Level

Knowledge levels of the nurse practitioners on various specific Internet-related items are displayed in Table 6. The Likert scale of 1 (*do not know*) to 5 (*great deal of knowledge*) was used to answer these questions. *Some knowledge* was reported most frequently by nurse practitioners in three areas: use of the Internet by the adolescent patient for health information (38.1%), links or names of reputable websites (52.4%), and navigating the Internet to identify health websites (45.0%). A *great deal of knowledge* (28.6%) was the most frequent response to knowledge of how to evaluate a website as being trustworthy.

Table 6

Nurse Practitioners' Knowledge Level of Health Education on the Internet

	Knowledge Level				
	Don't know	Very little	Some	Adequate	Great deal
Use of the Internet by adolescent for health information	3 (14.3%)	6 (28.6%)	8 (38.1%)	4 (19.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Links to or names of reputable health websites for teens.	1 (4.8%)	5 (23.8%)	11 (52.4%)	3 (14.3%)	1 (4.8%)
How to evaluate a health website as being trustworthy	1 (4.8%)	4 (19.0%)	5 (23.8%)	5 (23.8%)	6 (28.6%)
Policies within your workplace regarding Internet websites as sources of health education	11 (55.0%)	2 (10.0%)	1 (5.0%)	2 (10.0%)	4 (20.0%)
Navigating the Internet to identify health websites.	4 (20.0%)	1 (5.0%)	9 (45.0%)	2 (10.0%)	4 (20.0%)
Use of any health education based mobile applications.	4 (19.0%)	4 (19.0%)	6 (28.6%)	5 (23.8%)	2 (9.5%)

Note. Data reported as frequency (valid %). Mode indicated by bold font.

In order to examine the subjects' knowledge regarding the use of online health resources in their practice, a series of six knowledge items were developed assessing domains such as how to evaluate health websites' trustworthiness and workplace policies regarding Internet-based health education materials. Nurse practitioners were able to select responses that ranged from 1 (*do not know*) to 5 (*great deal of knowledge*).

The decision was made a priori to examine the six items for internal consistency among responses prior to combining them as a scale. Cronbach's alpha revealed adequate internal consistency ($\alpha = .87$) with single-item deletions making negligible improvements to the scale's internal consistency. As a result, all six questions were combined into a single, overall knowledge scale with possible scores ranging from 6 to 30 points.

A series of independent samples *t* tests were conducted to examine the relationship between nurse practitioners' self-reported online health resource knowledge and practice. The first test revealed a statistically significant difference ($F = -2.52, df = 13.54, p = .03$) in knowledge between nurse practitioners who reported that they had a specific health website to refer adolescent patients to and those who did not (see Table 7). Because an overall difference in knowledge was detected, a series of post-hoc analyses were then run to examine how each of the specific knowledge questions differed between those with and without a website to refer adolescent patients to (see Table 7). However, when the knowledge of nurse practitioners who routinely ask their patients whether they use the Internet to seek out health care information ($M = 11.33, SD = 5.13$) was compared to those who do not ask this ($M = 11.00, SD = 6.19$), no difference in overall knowledge levels were reported, $t(18) = -.09, p = .93$. However, this result may be attributable, in part, to the low frequency of nurse practitioners reporting routinely asking their patients about this ($n = 3$).

In addition, a Spearman correlation revealed a statistically significant, moderate, negative correlation between nurse practitioners' ratings of their concern about their

Table 7

Comparison of Knowledge Between Nurse Practitioners With and Without a Web Resource to Refer Adolescent Patients to

Variable	Have Website to Refer Adolescent Patients To ^a		Test statistic	df	Sig.	Effect Size ^b
	No	Yes				
Overall knowledge	8.10 (3.41)	14.00 (6.57)	-2.52	13.54 ^c	.03	1.13
Patients' health website use	1.45 (1.04)	1.80 (0.92)	-0.81	19	.43	0.36
Names of reputable health websites	1.55 (0.82)	2.30 (0.82)	-2.10	19	.05	0.91
How to evaluate health websites	2.18 (0.98)	2.90 (1.45)	-1.34	19	.20	0.58
Workplace health website policies	0.50 (1.08)	2.10 (1.85)	-2.36	14.48	.03	1.06
Finding health websites	1.40 (1.08)	2.70 (1.34)	-2.40	18	.03	1.07
Use of health mobile applications	1.55 (1.13)	2.20 (1.40)	-1.19	19	.25	0.51

^aReported as Mean (*SD*).

^bReported as Cohen's *D*.

^cThe assumption of the equality of variance was violated, so degree of freedom were adjusted.

ability to judge the accuracy of the health information on the Internet and their self-rated knowledge of web-based health resources (*r* ranged from -.43 to -.51, all *ps* < 0.05).

Another aspect of inquiry was applied to awareness of agency site or guides for evaluating the accuracy of health information online. Table 8 shows that of all the agencies listed, the Food and Drug Administration (63.2%), the National Institutes of Health (66.7%), and the National Library of Medicine (66.7%), were the most familiar to the nurse practitioners. Over half of the sample group (52.9%) had knowledge of the

Table 8

Nurse Practitioners' Awareness of Agencies With Internet Health Information Guidelines

Agency/Guidelines	<i>n</i> = # answering item	Yes <i>n</i> (%)	No <i>n</i> (%)
Health on the Net (HON) website accrediting organization	19	2 (10.5%)	17 (89.5%)
Medical Library Association (MLA) user guide	19	6 (31.6%)	13 (68.4%)
Food and Drug Administration	19	12 (63.2%)	7 (36.8%)
National Institutes of Health, National Library of Medicine	18	12 (66.7%)	6 (33.3%)
American Medical Association (AMA) guidelines	17	9 (52.9%)	8 (47.1%)

guidelines from the American Medical Association. Unfamiliar to many of the nurse practitioners in this sample were the Health on the Net website accrediting organization (89.5%) and the Medical Library Association user guide (68.4%).

Barriers and Facilitators to Use of Websites in the Practice Setting

Respondents were asked to list at least three barriers and three facilitators to the use of health education websites in the practice setting (Table 9). The top three responses listed as barriers by the 23 nurse practitioners in this study included time constraints (26.0%), lack of access to a computer at worksite or home for the adolescent (30.0%), and the adolescent's unclear knowledge of information found online (30.0%). Some of the other issues noted by these nurse practitioners included credibility/likability of websites, ability of teens to navigate websites, and the uncertainty that adolescents would access sites. Workplace concerns were reported by some respondents. The specific

Table 9

Barriers and Facilitators to Use of Health Education Websites as Resources in Practice

Barriers and Facilitators	<i>n</i> (%)
Barriers (<i>n</i> = 23)	
Time constraints	6 (26.0%)
Lack of access to computer (at worksite or home)	7 (30.0%)
Ability to navigate	2 (8.7%)
Credibility of sites	2 (8.7%)
Adolescent knowledge level	7 (30.0%)
Uncertainty issues with adolescent	2 (8.7%)
Other ^a	3 (13.0%)
Facilitators (<i>n</i> = 23)	
Provider involvement	5 (21.7%)
Provider recommendation	2 (8.7%)
Practice involvement (having information in current electronic medical record system, administration support)	3 (13.0%)
Time	2 (8.7%)
Equipment availability (computer, tablet, smartphone)	5 (21.7%)
List of sites	3 (13.0%)
Other ^b	2 (8.7%)

^aApproval from management (*n* = 1), reimbursement (*n* = 1), and provider seen as unprofessional (*n* = 1).

^bAbility to provide information confidentially (*n* = 1) and cost effective—save on paper use in office (*n* = 1).

concerns addressed were approval from management, reimbursement, and activities of the practitioner seen as unprofessional.

The top two facilitators that this group of nurse practitioners reported included the availability of having a computer, tablet, or smartphone (21.7%) and the willingness of the provider to be involved in improvement of care to adolescents (21.7%). Other facilitators mentioned included the need for practice involvement such as administration support, incorporating websites into the current electronic medical record system, and granting time. A list of sites and provider recommendations as well as the ability for

information to be confidential also ranked as important facilitators by some nurse practitioners to using health education websites in the workplace.

Benefits and Disadvantages of Using Websites for Adolescent Patients

Two questions at the end of the questionnaire asked respondents to list at least three benefits and at least three disadvantages of using health education websites for the adolescent patient. Results concerning benefits and disadvantages are listed in Table 10. The benefits that this sample of nurse practitioners ranked as the top three were there would be an increase in knowledge by using adolescent friendly websites (26.0%), adolescents would become more health aware and may even change behaviors (21.7%), and there would be an added advantage of educating peers and family members who also look at websites (21.7%). The ability for teens to access information on their own and at any time, that the information is adolescent focused, and the confidential aspect of the information were three key points mentioned by some of the nurse practitioners as beneficial. Other benefits included enhancing patient education, accessing information quickly and easily, and having informed adolescents come to appointments with questions.

The most frequently listed disadvantages to using health education websites with adolescents included language/literacy differences (21.7%) and possible delay in seeking treatment or self-diagnosis (17.4%). There was also concern from the nurse practitioners about decreased face-to-face time with patients, misinterpretation of findings by adolescents, or adolescents retrieving incorrect information. Practitioners also believed they were at a disadvantage because they were unable to monitor sites or had no time to view websites.

Table 10

Benefits and Disadvantages to Use of Health Education Websites With Adolescent Patients

Benefits and Disadvantages	<i>n</i> (%)
Benefits (<i>n</i> = 23)	
Adolescents can access on own	3 (13.0%)
Confidentiality	2 (8.7%)
Increase knowledge	6 (26.0%)
Educating peers/family	5 (21.7%)
Access later	2 (8.7%)
Adolescent focused information	4 (17.4%)
Decrease office resources and provider time	3 (13.0%)
Adolescent health awareness/change in behavior	5 (21.7%)
Other ^a	4 (17.4%)
Disadvantages (<i>n</i> = 23)	
Delay in seeking treatment/self-diagnose	4 (17.4%)
Decrease face to face time	2 (8.7%)
Misinterpretation of findings	3 (13.0%)
Inability for teen to ask questions	2 (8.7%)
Incorrect information	3 (13.0%)
Parent monitoring	2 (8.7%)
Language/Literacy differences (to high level, illiteracy)	5 (21.7%)
Provider has no time to view/monitor sites	3 (13.0%)
Other ^b	2 (8.7%)

^aLess anxiety about health (*n* = 1), teen comes to appointment with questions (*n* = 1), enhances patient education (*n* = 1), and access information quickly and easily (*n* = 1).

^bFalse sense of hope (*n* = 1) and teen has no consistent access to technology (*n* = 1).

DISCUSSION

The Internet is often used by adolescents to obtain health information. Nurse practitioners who deliver care to adolescents should be aware of what adolescents are looking at online and also be comfortable with discussing and recommending appropriate health education websites. Most of the nurse practitioners in this study had access to a computer and the Internet and were quite confident with using computer technology. This group was fairly knowledgeable about how to find and judge health information on the Internet and felt confident in their skills. In general, the respondents felt confident at being able to evaluate a website for content. The group of nurse practitioners as a whole believed that using this technology would make their job easier and enhance the teaching time spent with adolescents. They felt that they would use Internet health education in their practices.

Based on the adapted technology acceptance model used in this study as a framework, perceived usefulness by the nurse practitioner and perceived ease of use by the nurse practitioner are the primary influences in the decision to use technology. The findings in this study indicate that there is a positive relationship between perception of usefulness of Internet health resources and use of those resources in both the professional and personal lives of these nurse practitioners. They also demonstrated that their ease of use led to an increased use of the Internet for themselves, family, and friends in the last month as well as in the last 3 months. Of interest, when evaluating ease of use of the Internet for health resources and frequency of sharing this information with patients, the nurse practitioners showed a significant correlation only at the 3-month mark and not at 1 month.

This sample group of nurse practitioners concluded that teens were seeking information on the Internet, yet a majority of the nurse practitioners reported that they did not discuss websites with their adolescent patients and did not ask adolescents about health education websites they frequented. This could be based on the nurse practitioner's lack of knowledge about the importance of guiding adolescents to reliable sites since adolescents may be getting their information from untrustworthy Internet sources. Nurse practitioners who did refer teens to specific websites seemed to be more knowledgeable about workplace policies, searching out websites, and knowing of specific websites. Without knowledge in these three arenas, nurse practitioners did not recommend websites for the adolescent. Nurse practitioners in this study realized teens are seeking out information online but appeared to be uncertain about how to address the issue and also believed there were obstacles to making Internet health education a part of their routine practice. On the positive side, nurse practitioners saw some advantages to the use of online resources as well.

Comparison to Previous Research Studies

Barriers and Facilitators

Certain responses from nurse practitioners in this study in regard to the use of health education websites in their practice settings mirrored that of previous research discussed in the literature review. When evaluating barriers to using websites, some of the common concerns were the adolescent's ability to understand the information. This was one of the areas mentioned in McMullan's (2006) review of articles. Another area of concern was the time constraint of practitioners, which was mentioned in both McMullan's and in Kurki et al.'s (2011) research. In regard to facilitators to use in

practice, both the nurse practitioners in this study and the nurses in Kurki et al.'s study believed that adequate resources like a computer, smartphone, and tablet and a willingness or knowledge of the Internet aid in the Internet's use in the practice setting.

Benefits and Disadvantages

Using health education websites as a tool for working with adolescents has both its benefits and disadvantages. In comparing this study's results related to the benefits of Internet use with other research done with adolescents, a few similarities arise.

Adolescents in two of the studies in the literature review communicated that they wanted quick, easy, and confidential information (Selkie et al., 2011; Smart et al., 2012), and the nurse practitioner respondents in this study also listed these as benefits to the use of websites. The respondents in this study stated that the increase in health knowledge of the adolescent may lead to a possible change in behavior, paralleling the findings in the Kaiser Family Foundation survey (Rideout, 2001).

The disadvantages reported by the nurse practitioners in this study were similar to ones noted in previous literature. Decreased face-to-face time with the adolescent was stated here as well as by nurses in Kurki et al.'s (2011) study. A major disadvantage seen in this study and also in much of the previous research on this topic was the retrieval of inaccurate information off the Internet by the adolescent (Emond et al., 2013; Kurki et al., 2011; McMullan, 2006; Wald et al., 2007). Nurse practitioners in this study were concerned about adolescents using the Internet to self-diagnose and treat themselves; this same concern was brought up in McMullan's (2006) study as well. These disadvantages and barriers need to be addressed to move the Internet forward into a daily routine for

practitioners. Supporting the adolescent in safe Internet usage requires knowledge and time on the part of the practitioner.

Limitations

This study had limitations. The small sample size affects the ability to generalize to the general population of nurse practitioners. The use of convenience sampling and network sampling can lead to a sampling bias. In addition, recruiting on Facebook and using a web-based questionnaire are two aspects that may have biased the sample in that primarily Internet savvy individuals would feel comfortable with this platform.

Recommendations and Implications for Practice

The Internet has the potential to be a powerful tool in patient education for the adolescent. In using appropriate health resource Internet sites, the younger generation can be empowered with health information to change unfavorable health behaviors to favorable health behaviors. The provider-adolescent relationship can be strengthened, which can enhance communication between patient and provider. This study shows that the nurse practitioner needs to be equipped with the appropriate knowledge and tools to assist adolescents in choosing appropriate websites.

One solution would be the integration of appropriate websites into present clinical computer management systems within practice settings. Additionally, the system could have reminders to providers to make sure they are asking adolescents about websites and access to patient portals to communicate confidentially appropriate websites directly to adolescents. Another solution could be the development of medical applications (apps) that can be recommended and accessible to adolescents.

Other interventions that would assist providers in developing knowledge and confidence in recommending websites to adolescents are the following: (a) improving the accessibility of tools for nurse practitioners that provide guidelines on appropriate websites which include content and reliability information and (b) developing provider education covering existing help on the Internet like the Health on the Internet Foundation Code of Conduct (HONcode) and Medical Library Association guidelines.

For further research, it would be interesting to investigate whether age of provider demonstrates a relationship with Internet use. Also studying the impact of medical apps on adolescent health education may provide beneficial findings for health care professionals with implications for practice change. Evaluating providers who are successfully using the Internet as health education with their patients would be quite valuable as well.

This study leads to some insights with regard to incorporation of health care websites into a nurse practitioner's routine care of the adolescent. The perception of usefulness and ease of use of these websites by practitioners will lead to the integration of health care websites into their current practice. The comfort and knowledge of appropriate health care websites to refer adolescents to are essential in the nurse practitioner's success in this endeavor.

Dissemination of Project Findings

With the data collected from this study, this researcher intends to submit a manuscript for publication in a professional journal to inform others of the findings and to present the study at a nursing research conference. The results of this study will also be shared with the CANP local chapter. In addition, a request will be sent

out to members for interested nurse practitioners to become involved in developing an educational tool for nurse practitioners that features trustworthy Internet health links and resources for adolescents. The educational tool can include (a) guidelines for evaluating health education websites and (b) a list of trustworthy websites that a nurse practitioner can recommend to a teen patient.

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APPENDIX A**QUESTIONNAIRE*****HEALTH EDUCATION INFORMATION ON THE INTERNET (HEII)*****Health Education Information on the Internet (HEII)**

The aim of this questionnaire is to investigate the knowledge and use of the internet by nurse practitioners. In particular, the investigation is focused on health education for the adolescent who are between the ages of 13 and 18 years.

Demographics

1. Age

- 20-25
- 26-30
- 31-35
- 36-40
- 41-45
- 46-50
- 51-55
- 56-60
- 61-65
- 66-70
- 70+

2. Gender

- Male
- Female

3. Please choose one term that best describes you.

- White (Caucasian)
- Latino or Hispanic
- Chinese or Chinese American
- Vietnamese or Vietnamese American
- Black or African American
- Pacific Islander
- Other

Clarify: _____

4. Education: Please circle the number years of school

13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24 25 26 27 28 29 30

5. Choose a specialty area(s) that most closely describes your practice. (Check all that apply.)

- Family practice
- Acute Care
- Pediatrics
- Obstetrics/Gynecology
- Geriatrics
- Hospice
- Case Management
- Community/Public health
- Mental Health
- Other

Clarify: _____

6. What setting do you practice in?

- Retail health
- Ambulatory/Primary care
- Community/School Clinic
- Private practice
- Hospital
- Other

Clarify: _____

7. Please specify how many years you have been in practice as a nurse practitioner

8. Please supply the average number of adolescent patients (ages 13-18) that you see in your practice weekly_____

1. As you look through these items, please mark 'yes' if you have one of these or 'no' if you do not. Do you have a...?

Cell phone	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Smartphone	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
PDA	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Desktop Computer	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Laptop Computer	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Tablet Computer	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No

2. Do you have access to a computer at home?

Yes No

3. Do you have access to the internet at home?

Yes No

If yes, how often do you access the internet? Circle the one choice that best describes your use of the internet:

Daily Weekly Monthly

4. Do you have access to a computer at work?

Yes No

5. Do you have access to the internet at work?

Yes No

If yes, how often do you access the internet? Circle one:

Daily Weekly Monthly

6. How available is internet access for you at your work setting? Circle the one choice that best describes the availability:

Not at all/seldom/about half the time/usually/always

7. Within your workplace, do you use electronic medical records?

Yes No

8. How would you rate your level of confidence with using computer technology? Circle the choice that best reflects your confidence level.

Not confident/ somewhat confident / confident /moderately confident /very confident

Please circle the choice that best reflects your response to the question posed.

9. Have you ever used the internet to get health information for yourself, friend, or family member?

In the last month:

Never/very rarely/rarely/occasionally/frequently/very frequently

In the last 3 months:

Never/very rarely/rarely/occasionally/frequently/very frequently

10. Have you ever used the internet to obtain health information resources to give to or share with your patients?

In the last month:

Never/very rarely/rarely/occasionally/frequently/very frequently

In the last 3 months:

Never/very rarely/rarely/occasionally/frequently/very frequently

Circle the choice that best describes your agreement with the following statements.

11. I feel confident in using the internet to gather trustworthy clinical information/health education.

Strongly disagree/disagree/undecided/agree/ strongly agree

12. It would be easy for me to become skillful at identifying health education websites on the internet that are appropriate for the adolescent.

Strongly disagree/disagree/undecided/agree/ strongly agree

13. I am concerned about my ability to judge the accuracy of the health information on the internet?

Strongly disagree/ disagree/undecided/ agree/strongly agree

14. Using health education websites would enhance my effectiveness in teaching the adolescent patient.

Strongly disagree/disagree/undecided/agree/ strongly agree

15. Using health education websites for the adolescent would make my job easier.

Strongly disagree/disagree/undecided/agree/ strongly agree

16. I believe it would benefit me as a health care provider to identify internet websites and resources that my adolescent clients could access for their benefit.

Strongly disagree/disagree/undecided/agree/ strongly agree

17. I am concerned about the ability of my adolescent patient to identify reliable health information on the internet.

Strongly disagree/ disagree/undecided/ agree/strongly agree

Please circle the choice that best reflects your response to the question posed.

18. How likely are you to use the internet to provide adolescents in your practice with healthcare information handouts or websites?

Not at all/slightly unlikely/neither unlikely or likely/ slightly likely/quite likely

19. Do your adolescent patients ever ask you about health information that they obtained from the internet?

Never/rarely/occasionally/frequently/very frequently

20. How many of the adolescent patients in your practice do you think routinely seek out health information on their own from internet resources?

None/Few/Some/Most/All/I don't know

21. Do your adolescent patients ever inquire as to what internet websites/resources would be valuable health information sources for them to access?

Never/very rarely/rarely/occasionally/frequently/very frequently

22. Have your adolescent patients talked to you about health education websites?

In the last month:

Never/very rarely/rarely/occasionally/frequently/very frequently

In the last 3 months:

Never/very rarely/rarely/occasionally/frequently/very frequently

If yes, which websites?

23. Have you discussed health websites with your adolescent patients?

In the last month:

Never/very rarely/rarely/occasionally/frequently/very frequently

In the last 3 months:

Never/very rarely/rarely/occasionally/frequently/very frequently

If yes, which websites?

24. Is there a specific internet health education website or websites that you recommend to adolescents?

Yes No

If yes, which website(s)?

25. Do you routinely ask teens during their office visit with you whether they use the internet to seek out healthcare information?

Yes No

If yes, what do you ask?

26. If you knew of a trustworthy website for adolescent health information on the internet, would you use it in your practice?

Not at all/slightly unlikely/neither unlikely or likely/ slightly likely/quite likely

How would you rate your level of knowledge about each of the following items:

	Do not know 1	Very little knowledge 2	Some knowledge 3	Adequate knowledge 4	Great deal of knowledge 5
27. Use of the internet by your adolescent patients to obtain personal health information.					
28. Links to or names of reputable health education websites for teens.					
29. How to evaluate a health website as being a trustworthy resource for information.					
30. Any policies within your workplace about recommending internet websites as sources of health education for adolescents.					
31. Navigating the internet to identify adolescent health websites.					
32. Use of any health education based mobile applications.					

33. Are you aware of any of the following agency sites or guides for evaluating the accuracy of health information online?

Health on the Net (HON) website accrediting organization	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Medical Library Association (MLA) user guide	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
Food and Drug Administration	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
National Institutes of Health, National library of Medicine	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
American Medical Association(AMA) guidelines	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No

34. What are the three key barriers to the use of health education websites as educational resources in your practice setting?

35. What do you see as the three top facilitators to the use of health education websites as educational resources in your practice setting? (Note you may list more than 3 if you like.)

36. What do you see as the three top benefits from using health education websites with your adolescent patients? (Note you may list more than 3 if you like.)

37. What do you see as the top three disadvantages to using health education websites with your adolescent patients? (Note you may list more than 3 if you like.)

APPENDIX B

INFORMED CONSENT

Nurse Practitioner Knowledge and Use of the Internet for Health Education with the Adolescent

What the study is about: Because you are a nurse practitioner that works with adolescents, you are being asked to participate in a study for a Doctoral Project for the Southern California CSU DNP Consortium. The purpose of this study is to learn about nurse practitioner's knowledge regarding health education information on the internet that is appropriate for adolescents. The adolescent is defined for this study as ages 13 through 18. The study is also investigating factors related to nurse practitioners seeking out reliable health education websites on the internet to recommend to their adolescent clients.

You will be asked to: If you agree to be in this study, you will be asked to fill out a paper and pencil questionnaire "Health Education Information on the Internet (HEII)". You will be asked to read and sign the consent form prior to completing the survey. This questionnaire will take approximately 15 minutes to complete. After completion of the survey, you will place both consent and survey in the designated envelopes and seal them. You will then place them in the collection box located in the back of the meeting room. If you are participating via the U.S mail, please place the consent form and survey in the separate pre-addressed, stamped envelopes provided and mail them separately.

Risks and benefits: There are minimal risks from participating in this study. These may include: Possible discomfort while completing the survey, loss of confidentiality could pose risk to professional reputation. There are no direct benefits from participating in the study. You may get gratification from knowing that you may be helping to determine the effectiveness of using internet health education for the adolescent population in a practice setting.

Your answers will be confidential. Your participation in this study is confidential. Please do not put your name or any other identifying information on the survey or the return envelope. Results will be publicly reported as group averages only. The data will be stored in a secured/password protected file. In the event of a publication or presentation resulting from the study, no personally identifiable information will be shared.

Voluntary participation: Your decision to be in this study is voluntary. You can stop at any time. You do not have to answer any questions you do not want to answer. Refusal to take part in or withdrawing from this study will involve no penalty or loss of benefits you would receive otherwise.

If you have questions: Please contact Cheryl Smythe-Padgham at (xxx)xxx-xxxx cspadgham@xxxxxxxxx or Margaret Brady RN, B.S.N., M.S., Ph.D. mabrady@xxxxxxxxx with questions or concerns about this study. If you have questions regarding your rights as a

research subject, contact the Office of University Research, CSU Long Beach, 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840; Telephone: (562) 985-5314 or email to irb@csulb.edu.

Thank you for your assistance.

I have read and understood this consent form, and I agree to participate in this study.

Participant Printed Name

Date

Participant Signature